

Source-Correction and Two-level Error Indicators for AMR Applied to Linear Short-Characteristics for the Solution of Discrete-Ordinates Transport Equation by Octree

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development and application of an adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) for solving the neutron transport equation using linear short-characteristics. Unlike traditional AMR techniques designed for finite element methods, this work introduces novel error indicators tailored for characteristic-based discretizations, where errors primarily stem from source term approximations. Two error estimation strategies are proposed: a *source-correction* indicator, inspired by transport cross-section corrections, and a *two-level* indicator leveraging on local mesh refinement. The AMR algorithm is implemented within the IDT code, using an octree structure to dynamically refine the spatial grid based on local error estimates. 3-D numerical results on torus-shaped source-problem demonstrate the method's effectiveness, achieving a 65% of reduction of the spatial degrees of freedom while maintaining the accuracy of a refined uniform mesh of voxels, taken as the reference. The results highlights the potential of AMR for improving computational efficiency in transport simulations without compromising accuracy.

Keywords: Adaptive mesh refinement, neutron transport, short-characteristics method, spatial discretization, error estimation

1. INTRODUCTION

The numerical resolution of the neutral-particle transport equation requires accounting for a very large number of degrees of freedom. This high dimensionality naturally leads to significant computational costs, both in terms of time and memory. Therefore, reducing the number of degrees of freedom, while maintaining a controlled degradation of the solution's accuracy, is a promising direction for improvement. One way to achieve such a reduction, and the one of interest here, is through the spatial variable using adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) methods. However, most existing AMR techniques are designed for finite elements and rely on *a priori* error analyses. Since the discretization error behaves differently in characteristic-based methods and, which origin relies on local source approximation, new error indicators must be developed.

Along a characteristic line, the transmitted flux, which is governed by the exponential attenuation, is solved analytically, and the error arises from the local truncation of the source. Consequently, the indicators must focus on this contribution. Furthermore, due to the nature of the method of characteristics, errors propagate; the indicators must therefore identify local sources of error without being affected by their propagation, in order to determine where further refinement is necessary. This implies that local variations of the spatial moments must be considered. The work presented in this paper extends previously conducted studies in a 1-D slab case. The transition to multi-dimensional problems introduces a new source of error associated with short characteristics, namely the discretization error on surfaces.

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Moreover, the introduction of non-conforming meshes causes a loss of information when passing from a finely meshed region to a coarser one, which can lead to an additional discretization error that must be considered.

After introducing the context of our work (namely, the resolution of source-driven problems using the short-characteristics linear method) we will briefly outline the error indicators we have developed, though space constraints prevent detailed discussion. We will then present the implementation of AMR within the CEA-developed code IDT, followed by encouraging results obtained on a 3D example.

2. ERROR ESTIMATION WITH THE LINEAR SHORT-CHARACTERISTIC METHOD

2.1. The IDT short-characteristic method

We focus our discussion on spatial discretization, which relies on linear short-characteristics. The latter uses multigroup approximation in energy and discrete-ordinates S_N method in angle. The spatial domain is partitioned into Cartesian meshes. For each cell, at every inner iteration and in each direction, we solve a system whose unknowns are the spatial Legendre moments of the cell-average flux and the of the outgoing surface flux. To do so, four matrices must be pre-computed, namely the transmission, escape, incoming, and collision matrices, see the theoretical manual. The system to be solved takes the following form for a given iteration, in a given cell, and for a given direction Ω of the S_N quadrature, which is considered fixed, one solves for

$$\begin{aligned}\psi &= \sum_{s'=x_{in},y_{in},z_{in}} \bar{\bar{\mathbf{I}}}_{s'} \psi^{s'} + \bar{\bar{\mathbf{C}}}q, \\ \psi^s &= \sum_{s'=x_{in},y_{in},z_{in}} \bar{\bar{\mathbf{T}}}_{s,s'} \psi^{s'} + \bar{\bar{\mathbf{E}}}_s q, \text{ for } s = x_{out}, y_{out}, z_{out}.\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Here, ψ is the vector of volume Legendre moments (4 spatial components for the linear case), ψ^s is the surface Legendre moments for the outgoing faces of cell (3 spatial components), $\psi^{s'}$ is for the surface moments on the entry sides and q the volume moments of the source. $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{I}}}_{s'}$ represents the contribution of the entry flux to the volume flux, $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{C}}}$ the contribution to the volume flux by volume source, $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{T}}}_{s,s'}$ the entry surface to the outgoing surface and finally $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{E}}}_s$ the volume source to the outgoing flux contribution.

In this cell, the local error is driven by the approximation on the source part, we can show, that approximation made on $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{E}}}_s q$ leads the error. Therefore it will be the main focus of our study.

2.2. Two indicators of the error

The AMR consists of dynamically adjusting the spatial grid based on the local requirements of the solution. Regions of the domain where the solution exhibits rapid and/or irregular changes requires finer mesh to accurately capture the gradient of the flux. Conversely, areas where the solution is relatively smooth are represented with coarser meshes to save computational resources. Therefore, AMR techniques require an evaluation of the local error to determine where refinement is necessary. For the transport equation, these techniques have traditionally been used in the context of FEM.

In the FEM context, the most common *a posteriori* methods use the residual of the equations. Due to the construction of these methods, the residual satisfies the same type of equation as the primary solution [1], and local evaluation of the solution provides a local approximation of the error. However, for characteristic methods, this approach may provide an insufficient error estimate, as the error accumulates from upstream to downstream regions.

A natural technique from discontinuous Galerkin methods is the use the flux jump at the boundary

of each cell, as in [2]. Unfortunately, this approach cannot be applied to MOC because it implies the analytical continuity of the solution along the characteristic line. A possible alternative could be to evaluate the jump in first-order Legendre coefficients between cells, as a measure of the gradient, but this approach has been proven poorly effective in 1D [3].

2.2.1. The source-correction indicator

The first indicator is the source corrected estimator, the principle is to bound the norm of the angular flux on the outgoing (+) surface $s = x, y, z$ by a *0-corrected* evaluation of the source such that the inequality $\|\psi_s^+ - \psi_{1,s}^+\| \leq \|\psi_{0-c,s}^+ - \psi_{0,s}^+\|$, where $\psi_{1,s}^+$, $\psi_{0,s}^+$ and $\psi_{0-c,s}^+$ are respectively the flux evaluated by the linear-source, the constant-source and the 0-corrected source expansions. To do so, we first evaluate the linear angular source, $Q(\mathbf{r}) = Q_0 + \mathbf{Q}_1 \cdot \bar{\bar{\Delta}} \cdot \mathbf{r}$, with \mathbf{r} as the spatial position taken from the centroid of the cell, while the matrix $\bar{\bar{\Delta}} = \text{diag}\{\frac{1}{\Delta_x}, \frac{1}{\Delta_y}, \frac{1}{\Delta_z}\}$ over the trajectory $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_s^+ - \Omega x$ of length $L = L(\mathbf{r}_s^+)$, where Q_0 and \mathbf{Q}_1 are the zero and linear moments of the source, respectively. Then, transforming the coordinate x along the trajectory, in the dimensionless coordinate $u \in [-1, 1]$, such that $x = \frac{L}{2}(u + 1)$, we can write the source integral as

$$\int_0^L dx e^{-\Sigma x} Q(L-x) = \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 du e^{-\frac{L\Sigma}{2}(1+u)} Q\left(\frac{L}{2}(1-u)\right). \quad (2)$$

We write $Q(u)$ for $Q(\frac{L}{2}(1-u))$ and we approximate the source over trajectory t by the linear expansion, $Q_1(u) = Q_0^t + Q_1^t u$, and the *0-corrected* source, $Q_{0-c}(u) = (Q_0^t - \frac{Q_1^t}{3}) + \frac{2}{3}Q_1^t \delta(u+1)$, where the zero and linear moments along trajectory t are respectively

$$\begin{aligned} Q_0^t &= Q_0 + \mathbf{Q}_1 \cdot \bar{\bar{\Delta}} \cdot (\mathbf{r}_s^+ - \frac{L}{2}\Omega), \\ Q_1^t &= -\frac{L}{2}\mathbf{Q}_1 \cdot \bar{\bar{\Delta}} \cdot \Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

We replace the expansions (3) into the source integral (2), and integrate over the outgoing surface s to catch the zero-order contribution of the source on the outgoing flux as,

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{s,0,Q_1}^+ &= E_{0,s}Q_0 + \mathbf{Q}_1 \cdot \bar{\bar{\Delta}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{1,s}, \\ \psi_{s,0,Q_{0-c}}^+ &= E_{0,s}Q_0 + \mathbf{Q}_1 \cdot \bar{\bar{\Delta}} \cdot \left[\mathbf{E}_s^+ - \frac{\Omega}{3}(E_s(L) + V_s) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where the escape coefficients E are defined by (here, symbol \mathbf{E} stands for a 3-D vector)

$$\begin{aligned} E_{0,s} &= \int_{\Gamma_s} d\mathbf{r}_s^+ |\Omega \cdot \mathbf{n}_s| \frac{(1 - e^{-\Sigma L})}{\Sigma} & E_s(L) &= \int_{\Gamma_s} d\mathbf{r}_s^+ |\Omega \cdot \mathbf{n}_s| L \frac{(1 - e^{-\Sigma L})}{\Sigma} \\ \mathbf{E}_{1,s} &= \mathbf{E}_s^+ - \Omega \int_{\Gamma_s} d\mathbf{r}_s^+ |\Omega \cdot \mathbf{n}_s| \int_0^L dx e^{-\Sigma x} x & \mathbf{E}_s^+ &= \int_{\Gamma_s} d\mathbf{r}_s^+ |\Omega \cdot \mathbf{n}_s| \mathbf{r}_s^+ \frac{(1 - e^{-\Sigma L})}{\Sigma}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The residual $\eta_{sc} = |\psi_{s,0,Q_1}^+ - \psi_{s,0,Q_{0-c}}^+|$ is thus evaluated as

$$\eta_{sc} = \left| \mathbf{Q}_1 \cdot \bar{\bar{\Delta}} \cdot \left[\mathbf{E}_{1,s} - \mathbf{E}_s^+ + \frac{\Omega}{3}(E_s(L) + V_s) \right] \right| \quad (6)$$

where $V_s = \int_{\Gamma_s} d\mathbf{r}_s^+ |\Omega \cdot \mathbf{n}_s| L$ is the volume subtended by surface s along direction Ω . If the cell is a voxel, as in our case $\Delta_x = \Delta_y = \Delta_z = \Delta$, and it is optically thin, such that $\tau = \Delta\Sigma \ll 1$, then the error indicator is evaluated by Taylor expansion, as

$$\eta_{sc} = \left| \frac{\mathbf{Q}_1 \cdot \bar{\Delta} \cdot \bar{\Omega}}{36\Sigma} \right| \tau^3 + o(\tau^3). \quad (7)$$

2.2.2. The two-level indicator

The other indicator is what we called the *two-level* indicator. This indicator is more classical in the way that it used a refined solution to compute the local error. However, the solution doesn't need to be refined globally but only locally. Each cell is cut in eight, the coarse cell is the level 0 and the refined cells form the level 1. The order of the cell is shown in the figure 1, they are ordered in binary with three digits, from 000 to 111, each digits represent an axis in the order *zyx*.

Figure 1. Splitting of a cell

This indicator is also based on the local Legendre development on the cell. The principle is to interpolate the quadratic Legendre coefficients on level 0 using the linear coefficient of the level 1 and then to use those coefficients in an approximation of the quadratic escape term. The first step is the estimation of the quadratic coefficient of the source. There are 6 quadratic Legendre coefficients, one per axis (noted Q_{2xx}, Q_{2yy} and Q_{2zz}) and three crossed-axis (Q_{2xy}, Q_{2yz} and Q_{2xz}). Each cell on the level 1 has 3 linear coefficients, noted $Q_{1x}^{000}, Q_{1y}^{000}, Q_{1z}^{000}, Q_{1x}^{001}$ etc. After some algebra and using a Taylor expansion, we find out the approximation in 8.

The second step is to compute the quadratic terms of the escape coefficients by assembling linear terms of the 8 refined cells. This was done numerically using symbolic calculation with the *sympy* Python library. For brevity, we give here the final result:

$$\eta_{2l} = \left(\frac{1}{3}(Q_{1x}^{100} - Q_{1x}^{000} + Q_{1y}^{010} - Q_{1y}^{000} + Q_{1z}^{001} - Q_{1z}^{000}) + Q_{1x}^{010} - 2Q_{1x}^{000} + Q_{1y}^{001} - Q_{1y}^{000} \right) \frac{\tau^2}{18\Sigma}. \quad (9)$$

This indicator should give a better estimation, but the approximation can be quite approximated for some direction. Some additional work needs to be done to better take into account the effect of the angle on the estimator.

3. THE AMR ALGORITHM

The two error indicators presented in this work are used to drive the AMR. Since AMR concerns the spatial variable, its integration is achieved by modifying the inner iterations, particularly the sweeping algorithm. The implementation is written in Fortran, within the IDT code [4]. In this context, the code works on a grid of voxels. For the AMR algorithm by *otree*, this grid needs to be of size 2^{3N} i.e 2^N voxels per X/Y/Z axis. The so-called level N specifies the resolution of the voxelized geometry received as the

input. Therefore, such a *maximum*, or refined level of the algorithm, is the grid used to input data and output results.

As in the classical sweeping method applied to XYZ geometries, AMR is performed octant by octant. The data structure is constructed using *octrees*, [5], starting from the root, the so-called level-0, which represents the entire spatial domain within a single cell. Then, the cell is split, if necessary, creating new leaves on the octree. For a given level n , a cell- n is split either because it is heterogeneous, hence the underlying levels $\geq (n + 1)$ are not composed of a single material, or because the error indicators tell that the residual is too large with respect to user's tolerance. This process is performed recursively until no cell needs to be refined. The algorithm also stops when the maximum level of splitting, i.e. N , is reached. As said, the latter coincides with the most refined voxel belonging to the uniform grid of voxels given as the input.

The algorithm relies on a recursive function that receives a cell and subdivides it into 8 when necessary. It works on two levels, as presented in the figure 1. The incorporation of the recursive sweep into the inner iterations is detailed in Algorithm 1, and the sweep itself in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 1: Structure of the inner iterations

```

Init of empty octrees, one per octant;
while  $i \leq max\_inner$  or  $\|1 - \frac{\phi^{(i+1)}}{\phi^{(i)}}\| > tol_{inners}$  do
  Update of the sources with the flux moments
  for ( $octant = 1, 8$ ) do
    Compute directional sources over the octant
    Call recursive sweeping of the octant (for all directions of the octant)
    Update the angular moments of the flux with the results of each octant
  end for
  Compute of the inner iteration residual,  $\|1 - \frac{\phi^{(i+1)}}{\phi^{(i)}}\|, i = i + 1$  .
end while

```

4. THE STUDY CASE AND THE NUMERICAL RESULTS

The simulations are carried on a torus centered inside a cube of water. The total length of each side of the cube is 20 m , the outermost and the radii of the torus are 6 m and 2 m . This geometry is modeled using cubic voxels of equal size using an octree of $N = 6$ levels. There are $2^6 = 64$ voxels per side, for a total of 262.144 voxels. The torus is made of U-Th molten salt (F-Li-Be with fluorides of zirconium, uranium and thorium) and the exterior of the torus is made of water. Vacuum boundary conditions are set over all the faces.

The angular quadrature used in the simulations is the 12×12 Chebyshev-Legendre quadrature, which comprises 288 directions. A 7-group cross-section library is considered, obtained by energy-collapse of 281-group Fine-Structure self-shielded cross sections. Since we focus on source-problems, the fission in the torus zone was removed and substituted by a spatially uniform Watt source.

Since the spatial sweeping is simultaneously performed along all directions of a given octant, the error indicator catches the maximum error observed among all directions of the octant. Therefore, because the voxelized torus is slightly non-symmetrical, the number of voxels computed along each octant is not constant. The computed non-conforming mesh is thus automatically specialized per octant. Figure 2 shows the mean value of the depth per voxel for the thermal group 7. We observe that maximum depth is reached on the interface between the surface of the torus and the surrounded water. This enforces the idea that the geometrical gradient due to material discontinuities are predominant in such a problem. The computed scalar flux for the same energy group is given in Fig. 3. By comparing the two plots, a

Algorithm 2: The Recursive sweeping algorithm

SUBROUTINE RecursiveSweeping**if** The current cell is a leaf of the octree **then** **if** The cell is homogeneous **then** // Computation on level 0 Projection of sources and boundary fluxes from the voxel grid (N -level) onto the current cell

Solving the transport Eq. 1 for the cell flux

if AMR with 0-corrected source indicator **then**

Compute error indicator on level 0, Eq. (6) or (7)

end if **if** AMR with the two-level indicator **then** // Computation on level 1

Projection of the sources and boundary from the voxel grid to current level (level 1 here)

Transport sweep, Eq. (1), on 8 cells of level 1,

Compute error indicator using level 1 results, Eq. (9)

end if **end if** **if** The cell is homogeneous and (indicator $\eta < tol$ or the current level is the N -level) **then**

Projection of the volume and boundary flux on the voxel level

RETURN

else Adding new leaf to the octree, go level- $(n + 1)$ **end if****else**

Call RecursiveSweeping with next child to solve

end if**END SUBROUTINE**

Figure 2. Mean of the depth in the octree for each voxel along the octant

Figure 3. Scalar flux for group 7

Figure 4. Relative error on each voxel in logarithmic scale - Two level estimator, group 7

greater number of computed cells seems to appear where the gradient of the flux is large. However, it is also evident that, such an interface zone, implies refinement because of the geometrical and material discontinuities. It is therefore difficult to determine whether the local refinement depends more on the geometric discontinuities than on the flux gradient.

Figure 4 plots the relative difference in logarithmic scale between an AMR solution (two level estimator, 45% computed cell) and reference solution obtained by a uniform grid of $2^{3 \times 6}$ voxels. Since the voxel mesh does not respect the geometrical symmetry of the torus (as mentioned before, the voxelized torus is slightly non-symmetrical), the error plot shows a slightly non-symmetrical distribution as well. However, the relative difference remains bounded in less than 5%, with a maximum of 4.4% in some peripheral zones. Moreover, close the torus-water interface, where material discontinuities and flux gradient occurs, the AMR solution reproduces almost the same accuracy as the reference solution.

Figure 5. Error norm as a function the (%) of AMR cells w.r.t $N = 6$ grids, i.e. $2^{3 \times 6}$ voxels.

We compared the two indicators, namely the *0-corrected* source and the *two-level* error indicators, by computing the norm of the error in L_∞ (here indicated as *norm sup*), L_1 and L_2 as a function of the number of computed cells. The results are plotted in Fig. 5, where the abscissa represents the (%) of the computed cells with respect to the 262 144 voxels of the original geometry. The three norms are the classical L_2 and L_1 norms of the relative-difference distribution, while the *norm sup* represents the maximum relative-difference among the voxels. This graph shows that the *0-corrected* source and the *two-level* estimators exhibit similar results. A noticeable results is represented by the behaviours of the two-level indicator with respect to the *0-corrected* source indicator: as shown in Fig. 5, the two-level indicator performs worse than source-correction in term of maximum relative error, whereas it performs globally better in terms of weak error norms (L_2 or L_1). It let us think that some edge-cases along some direction are not well-enough grasp by the two-level error estimator. Also the estimators are constructed to minimize the error on the moments, i.e the means of the flux and of the gradient on a cell. Overall, Figure 5 shows us that the AMR provide promising results in terms of reduction of the computational-cost. For example, using only the 65% of spatial degrees of freedom, we can keep the maximum local error bounded below the 5% while a global L_2 -norm error of 0.3% percent.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper shows a new AMR method tailored for the neutron and photon transport equation solved using linear short-characteristic. The proposed method introduces two innovative error indicators, namely the *0 – corrected* source indicator and the *two – level* indicator, to dynamically refine spatial discretization where needed, reducing computational costs while maintaining accuracy. Numerical results on a 3-D torus geometry demonstrate the effectiveness of the AMR approach in non trivial geometry, achieving up to a 65% reduction in degrees of freedom with errors remaining below 5% in maximum relative error and 0.3% in mean norms (L_1 or L_2). The implementation within the IDT code, using an *octree* structure, shows promising potential in term of reduction of the number of degree of freedom. For the moment, the computational time and memory usage with and without AMR are similar. To facilitate implementation in IDT, the AMR algorithm relies on the current IDT data structure in addition to the *octree* structure. In particular, the voxel grid is stored completely. Additional works needs to be done to assess the robustness of the method in terms of computational effectiveness. To fully exploit the method, a lot of implementation optimization needs to be done. The most critical improvement would be eliminating the voxel grid to maximize memory and computational efficiency gains.

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